

TOPIC: FEATURES OF THE STUDY OF THE SEMANTICS OF RUSSIAN VERBS THAT CONTROL THE DATIVE CASE, BASED ON DISTRIBUTIVE-TRANSFORMATIONAL AND COMPONENT ANALYSIS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069322>

Abstract

The specificity of teaching the Russian language as a Russian as a foreign language provides for teaching semantics, due to the lack of knowledge, skills and abilities among students of the Uzbek school and future specialists in various professions to recognize and produce the semantics of Russian verbs.

In this article, the author proposes an examination of a part of one class of verbs of feelings that control the dative case, based on distributive-transformational and component analysis.

Keywords: distribution, microsystem, component analysis, semantics, transformation.

Semantic classes of verbs govern the form of the dative case.

The following semantic classes are marked with the dative case:

1. Verbs like "open" - frankly express feelings or other information in front of any person

$C^3_{od\ d}$ before $C^3_{OD\ TV}$ $\longleftrightarrow$

2. Verbs like "present" - to speak about someone from any side, to give someone a verbal assessment

$C^3_{od\ d} + (\text{like } C^4\ B)$

3. Verbs like "advise", expressing the will of the subject

$C^2_{od\ d} + \text{neod } v/\text{inf}$

4. Verbs like "excuse" - inform someone about your decision, do not attach importance to his act or negative property

$C^2_{od\ d} + C^3_{neod\ in}$ $\longleftrightarrow$ $C^2_{OD\ V} + C^3_{neod\ in}$

1. Verbs like "open" - frankly express feelings or other information in front of any person

$C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_{neod\ in} + C^3_{od\ d}$ $\longleftrightarrow$ $C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_{neod\ in} + \text{before } C^3_{od}$

Verbs with the indicated syntactic features include: pronounce (to a casual acquaintance the pain of the soul), shout out (to the crowd the name of a traitor), pour out (a heartache to a friend), layout (to the investigator the whole truth), express (a cherished thought to a friend), etc. (24 lexeis)

The verb to express (something) is translated: aytmoq, birdirmoq, izhor, (bayon) qilmoq, gapirmoq, aytib (gapirib) bermoq. To tell your opinion - uz fikrini aytmoq, fikr bildirmoq; speculate - tahmin qilmoq, faraz qilmoq; say it all - xammasini aytib bermoq, oshkor qilmoq (ust.), fosh qilmoq bildirib quymoq; tell a secret - sirini oshkor qilib (bildirib) quymoq.

Saodat dugonasiga o'z fikrini aytdi.

$C_{bk} + C^2_{jk} + C^3_{carcasses\ to} + G$

Exercise 1. Compose sentences with these phrases according to the microsystem

$C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_{NEOD\ V} + C^3_{od\ d} \quad \leftarrow C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_{NEOD\ V} + BEFORE\ C^3_{od\ TV}$

to utter (to a casual acquaintance the pain of the soul)

paint (to people a shameful picture of their lives)

to expose (to posterity the customs of these centuries)

divulge (to the public someone else's secret)

Exercise 2. Choose the subject to the given phrases $C^1_{od\ them}$ - an animate noun in the nominative case, agree on the subject and predicate in gender, number and case. Explain the semantics of verbs.

pour out heartache to a friend, tell the investigator the whole truth, express a cherished thought to a friend, confess your sincere thoughts to a friend, divulge a secret to people, draw a happy future for your beloved.

Exercise 3. Write down the sentences, add $C^3_{od\ d}$ - an indirect object that answers the question to whom? Explain the semantics of these verbs.

Paul spoke... the truth. Maxim painted the events The daughter poured out her soul ... The engineer outlined ... the situation. Writer

(Dostoevsky, Tolstoy) exposed ... the mores of his age. The reactionaries divulged the secret ... The witness revealed ... the details of the crime. The leader set ... the next tasks.

Exercise 4. Transform sentences from exercises 2 and 3 according to this microsystem

$C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_{NEOD\ V} + C^3_{OD\ D} \quad C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_{NEOD\ V} + BEFORE\ C^3_{od\ tv}$

2. Verbs like "present" - to speak about someone from any side, to give someone a verbal assessment

$C^1_{one\ of\ them} + G + C^2_v + C^3_{od\ d} + (How\ C^4_v)$

The class with the indicated distributive formula includes: recommend (to the listeners of the lecturer as a well-known specialist), characterize (to the students of the new teacher as a great connoisseur of ancient history), introduce, recommend (to the director Petrov as an experienced philologist), introduce (the guest to those present as a connoisseur of Indian painting), recommend (to Dean Aleksandrov as a possible laboratory assistant), characterize (to students a new teacher as a great expert on ancient history) (6 leke)

The analyzed verbs have the meaning "to present, recommend" (Apresyan, 1967,182). Z.V. Nichman ascribes to them the meaning "to respond about someone from any side, to give someone a verbal assessment" (Nichman, 1966.51).

Dependent participants of the situation denoted by these verbs, in principle, can always change places, which finds its expression in the following quasi-transformation: The dean introduced the new teacher to the students as a great expert on ancient history The dean introduced the students to the new teacher as disciplined and enthusiastic people.

The verb to present is translated: tanitmok, tanishtirmoq, introduce yourself to the audience - tuplanganlarga uzini tanishtirmok. Here the translation of the verb is given in a reflexive form and it is important to present oneself - uzini tanishtirmoq.

In the Russian microsystem, someone $C^1_{od\ im}$ (subject) represents G (verb), someone C^2_v (object first), someone $C^3_{od\ dat}$ (object second in the dative case) and an object is optional, but possible how whom, how (From 4 c). The same construction is possible in the Uzbek language. For example Uqituvchi yangi uquvchini bolalarga alochi sifatida tanishtirdi.

$C^1_{bk} + C^2_{TK} + C^3_{jk} + C^4_{sifatida} + G$

The teacher introduced the new student to the children as an excellent student. In both Uzbek and Russian sentences, a further explanation is possible (from another school or another city), but this is no longer of any interest to us. It should be noted that in the Uzbek language the preposition "how" is replaced by the word "sifatida".

The possibility in some cases of transferring the translation of a sentence using a distributive formula facilitates the study of the semantics of verbs by our selected construction.

Exercise 1. Make sentences with the following verbs according to this distribution scheme

$C^1_{odim} + G + C^2_v + C^3_{ODIM} + (\text{How } C^4_v)$

Sample: The dean introduced the new teacher to the students as a great expert on ancient history.

recommend, characterize, recommend, present, recommend, characterize: to the audience of the lecturer as a well-known specialist, to the dean Alexandrov as a possible laboratory assistant, to the guest present as an expert on Indian painting, to the director Petrov as an experienced philologist.

3. Verbs like "advise" express the will of the subject, his will

$C^1_{odim} + G + C^2_{od d} + C^3_{neod v/inf}$

Verbs of the type "inform" adjoin verbs of the type "advise". The formal difference between the latter and the former lies in the fact that they are in place of the word form that "allows an indefinite form of the verb. For example, The doctor recommended him to walk/walk. The semantic specificity of these verbs lies in the fact that they do not mean the transfer of information, but the "transmission of the will" of the speaker, i.e. will. These verbs include: forbid (traitor return home / return home), forbid (extraneous entry), trust (employee receiving a salary), allow (sick walks), prohibit (sick smoking), allow (sick walks), recommend (retired occupation therapeutic gymnastics), entrust (to the old man caring for horses), Prescribe (walk the patient), advise (running to the brother), allow (the writer to move to the capital), recommend (rest to the visitor), advise (reading to the sister) (13 lexemes).

The verb to advise someone (with an indefinite form - maslahat (kengash bermoq, maslahat kŷrmoq. Advise to walk more - ko'proq sayr qilishni maslahat bermoq; I do not advise you to leave (men sening ketishingni maslahat ko'rmayman.

In Russian, a complete representation of the microsystem under study

$C^1_{odim} + G + C^2_{Rod d} + C^3_{neod in}$

in Uzbek it looks like this:

$C_{bk} + C^2_{qk} + C^3_{TK} + G$

The first object in Russian is expressed as an animate noun in the dative case, and in Uzbek (genitive) as a possessive (qaratqich kelishigi bilan) and as a natural phenomenon a verb at the end of a sentence. The verb is split into nominal and verbal parts.

Exercise 1. Write sentences by distributing them (on your own) according to the (distribution scheme) microsystem

$C^1_{odim} + G + C^2_{ODD} + C^3_{NEOD V/INF}$

$C^1_{odim} \quad G \quad C^2_{ODD} \quad C^3_{NEOD V/INF}$

Sample: The doctor advised Anwar to walk/walk.

forbid (return home / return home), allow the patient (walk / walk), advise the patient (smoking), recommend (retired gymnastics classes), advise (brother running), allow (writer moving to the capital), advise sister reading).

Exercise 2. Make sentences according to the distribution scheme $C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{od\ d} + C^3_{NEOD\ B}$ in which the following verbs-predicates would appear in combination with additions.

forbid, entrust, forbid, allow, instruct, advise, suggest, prescribe, recommend.

Exercise 3. Write down the sentences. Replace the complement expressed by the infinitive with a noun (in the wine case).

The mother advised her daughter to go to university. The teacher asked the students to complete additional tasks. The doctor forbade the patient to go outside. The duty policeman recommended the visitor to rest. Lyudmila Sergeevna advised her sister to read.

4. Verbs like "excuse" - tell someone about your decision not to attach importance to his act or negative property

$C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{od\ d} + C^3_{neod\ v}$ ← $C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{od\ v} +$ behind $C^3_{neod\ v}$

The class with the indicated syntactic features includes the verb to excuse (to him this act - him for this act) and to forgive.

The verb "excuse" is kechirmoq, avf etmoq, gunohidan utmoq. I will not excuse him for this uning bu ishini (kilmishini) kechira olmayman; to excuse the prank of youth - yoshligini nazarga olib shuxligini kechirmoq, see qabul qilmoq, domla uning uzrini qabul qildi - literally translated: the teacher accepted his apology (translation-Kh.Z) domla uning qilmishini avf etdi - the teacher forgave him for his act. The scheme $C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{od\ d} + C^3_{neod\ /c}$ in Russian corresponds to the scheme $C_{bk} + C^2_{qk} + C^3_{tk} + G$ in the Uzbek language, etc.

The established inventory of correspondence between the semantemes of verbs with their syntactic classes in Russian and Uzbek provides material for the correct interpretation of the semantics of Russian verbs by students.

The description we have made is not so much typological as lingua-didactic. Its task is to give bilinguals a reliable criterion for interpreting the semantics of Russian verbs, taking into account their native language.

Exercise 1. With the following phrases, make a sentence according to this distribution

$C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{od\ d} + C^3_{NEOD\ v}$ ← $C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{OD\ V} +$ BEHIND $C^3_{NEOD\ V}$ Translate the sentences into your native language.

Exercise 2. Read the sentences, select the subject (subject, predicate and predicate), the first and second actants (additions) in them and make sentences on the microsystem with the selected components; apply the transformation.

$C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{od\ d} + C^3_{NEOD\ V}$ ← $C^1_{od\ im} + G + C^2_{OD\ V} +$ BEHIND $C^3_{NEOD\ V}$

1. The people blamed Godunov for the death of Demetrius and could not forgive him for the death of the young prince. 2. Troekurov did not forgive this remark, the offended Dubrovsky left the house. 3. And, although the Hellenes literally deified the best athletes, they did not forgive them for cowardice and dishonesty. 4. I sighed with relief: the children have forgiven.

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